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Executive summary

This report contains the results of a study by TNO in the 2024. The purpose of this project was to investigate if lack of shipping capacity could be a barrier to uptake of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier in the coming decades. The topic was divided into four research questions, answers to which are summarized below.

What are the characteristics of the current fleet of vessels transporting ammonia?

The existing fleet of ammonia-carrying ships is relatively young, largely due to a surge in the construction of LPG carriers around 2014. Although the Clarkson's ship database lists 758 vessels as potentially suitable for ammonia transport, only an estimated 10 to 20 percent of these are currently used for this purpose.

What are the expected developments in the fleet between 2025 and 2050?

The ammonia shipping market is anticipated to expand at a moderate rate, with average annual growth of a few percentage points. Should demand for ammonia shipping rise, the repurposing of existing vessels or the construction of new LPG tankers could swiftly boost ammonia-carrying capacity. Newly built vessels could utilize ammonia as a low-emission marine fuel, similar to how LNG carriers use LNG as both cargo and fuel today. The average size of newly built ammonia carriers is expected to increase to between 50,000 Dead Weight Tonnes (DWT) and 60,000 DWT, or potentially even larger.

How do the developments in the fleet match with a high-growth scenario for the uptake of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier?

If ammonia becomes widely adopted as a hydrogen carrier, the demand for ammonia shipping could increase significantly in the coming decades. Under such scenario, maritime trade could increase very significantly from 17 million tons currently to 320 million tonnes in 2050. The required shipping capacity of around 400 can be expanded by building of new ships or repurposing of the existing LPG tanker fleet. The shipbuilding industry has demonstrated its ability to rapidly produce large numbers of LPG carriers in response to rising demand. Many existing ships are also capable of carrying ammonia, although they are currently used for other types of cargo. These ships could be repurposed for ammonia transport without significant modifications.

Under which circumstances will lack of shipping capacity be a barrier to the uptake of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier?

A shortage of shipping capacity is unlikely to be a major obstacle to the adoption of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier. Existing ships can be repurposed, or new ships can be constructed quickly to accommodate any foreseeable increase in demand. However, given the cyclical nature of the shipbuilding market and the tendency for vessel supply to lag during periods of rapid trade growth, there may be times when supply is constrained, leading to higher transport costs.

Managementsamenvatting

Dit rapport bevat de resultaten van een onderzoek van TNO uit 2024. Het doel van dit project was om te onderzoeken of gebrek aan scheepvaartcapaciteit de komende decennia een barrière kan vormen voor de introductie van ammoniak als waterstofdrager. Het onderwerp is onderverdeeld in vier onderzoeksvragen, waarvan de antwoorden hieronder worden samengevat.

Wat zijn de kenmerken van de huidige vloot schepen die ammoniak vervoeren?

De bestaande vloot van ammoniakschepen is relatief jong, grotendeels als gevolg van een sterke toename van de bouw van LPG-tankers rond 2014. Hoewel de scheepsdatabase van Clarkson honderden schepen bevat die geschikt zijn voor ammoniaktransport, wordt momenteel slechts een klein percentage hiervan gebruikt voor dit doel.

Wat zijn de verwachte ontwikkelingen in de vloot tussen 2025 en 2050?

De verwachting is dat de bestaande markt voor het transport van ammoniak zal groeien met een gemiddelde jaarlijkse groei van enkele procentpunten. Mocht de vraag naar ammoniakvervoer stijgen, dan zou de herbestemming van bestaande schepen of de bouw van nieuwe LPG-tankers de capaciteit voor het vervoer van ammoniak snel kunnen vergroten. Nieuw gebouwde schepen zouden ammoniak kunnen gebruiken als emissiearme scheepsbrandstof, vergelijkbaar met de manier waarop LNG-schepen LNG als vracht en brandstof gebruiken. De gemiddelde omvang van nieuw gebouwde ammoniaktankers zal naar verwachting toenemen tot tussen de 50.000 en 60.000 DWT, of mogelijk zelfs groter.

Hoe passen de ontwikkelingen in de vloot bij een sterk groeiscenario voor de opname van ammoniak als waterstoftransporteur?

Als ammoniak op grote schaal wordt toegepast als waterstofdrager, zou de vraag naar het vervoer van ammoniak de komende decennia aanzienlijk kunnen toenemen. De scheepsbouwindustrie heeft bewezen snel grote aantallen LPG-tankers te kunnen produceren als reactie op de stijgende vraag. Bovendien kunnen veel bestaande schepen ook ammoniak vervoeren, hoewel ze momenteel voor andere soorten lading worden gebruikt.

Onder welke omstandigheden zal een gebrek aan transportcapaciteit een barrière vormen voor de introductie van ammoniak als waterstoftransportschip?

Het is onwaarschijnlijk dat een tekort aan scheepscapaciteit een groot obstakel zal zijn voor de adoptie van ammoniak als waterstofdrager. Bestaande schepen kunnen een nieuwe bestemming krijgen, of er kunnen snel nieuwe schepen worden gebouwd om tegemoet te komen aan een voorzienbare toename van de vraag. Gezien het cyclische karakter van de scheepsbouwmarkt en de tendens dat het aanbod van schepen achterblijft tijdens perioden van snelle handelsgroei, kunnen er echter momenten zijn waarop het aanbod beperkt is, wat tot hogere transportkosten zal leiden.

1. Introduction

Ammonia (NH₃) is one of the world's most widely used chemicals. It is produced from hydrogen and nitrogen. Traditionally, the hydrogen needed for the reaction is produced from natural gas. Production therefore mainly happens in countries with large natural gas reserves. Ammonia can also be produced using 'green' hydrogen, which is created from water and 'green' electricity.

Global production of ammonia was around 150 million metric tons¹ in 2021 [1]. Most of this was used for fertilizer production [2], often at or close to the ammonia production location. Around 17 million metric tons of ammonia were exported in 2021, mainly by ships. Maritime transport of ammonia is a mature market which has existed for decades. Facilities for (un)loading and storing ammonia are available in ports all over the world.

Demand for maritime transport of ammonia is expected to grow

The global transition towards a low-carbon economy is likely to increase demand for ammonia production and shipping. There are two main reasons for this: ammonia's role as a hydrogen carrier and as a maritime fuel.

Ammonia can be used as a so-called 'hydrogen carrier'. Hydrogen is difficult to transport over long distances, because it must be stored either at very low temperatures or at very high pressure. Converting hydrogen to ammonia makes it much easier to store and transport, since ammonia can be stored in liquid form at -33 °C and at atmospheric pressure. Ammonia also contains much more energy per unit of volume than hydrogen (either in liquid or in compressed form). For these reasons, conversion to ammonia is a way of facilitating long-distance hydrogen transportation.

Ammonia is also being considered as a future maritime fuel. The maritime industry uses roughly 250 million tonnes of fuel per year, containing 9,5 TJ of potential energy. If ammonia replaces a portion of this fuel, demand for ammonia production and distribution will increase significantly.

Because of ammonia's role in the energy transition production and trade volume of ammonia is expected to grow significantly. That would also mean a large increase in demand for maritime ammonia transportation. Therefore, the aim of this task is to identify whether maritime transport capacity is a barrier for the transition to green hydrogen.

Research questions

The following research questions will be answered in this analysis:

- What are the characteristics of the current fleet of vessels transporting ammonia?
- What are the expected developments in the fleet between 2025 and 2050?
- How do the developments in the fleet match with a high-growth scenario for the uptake of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier?
- Under which circumstances will lack of shipping capacity be a barrier to the uptake of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier?

¹ All weight volumes in this report refer to metric tons or tonnes.

Methodology

The following steps were taken in this study.

1. Identification of current ammonia trade volumes and an analysis of the current shipping fleet in both number of vessels and transport capacity.
2. Analysis of the expected fleet development
3. Development of demand scenarios for ammonia shipping to 2050 based upon existing forecast studies
4. Identify possible risks and barriers by performing a literature review.

For these steps, we consulted several databases and statistical sources (Clarkson's World shipping database, UNCTAD, Comext), literature on LPG Carriers and ammonia transport, as well as several forecast studies for the ammonia market and the development of worldwide production of synthetic hydrogen.

2. Transport of ammonia by ships

Ammonia transportation volumes

In 2021, global production of ammonia was around 150 million metric tons [1]. Around 90% of ammonia produced is for local use or use in integrated plants, mainly for production of fertilizers and as input for local industries. The remaining 10% is transported for use elsewhere.

17 million tonnes (25 million cubic metres) of ammonia was traded internationally in 2021 [3]. Figures on global trade for 2022 and beyond are not yet available, but World Bank data shows that due to the War in Ukraine, prices for ammonia soared, and most likely, trade volumes were much lower than before.

Production of ammonia mainly happens in countries which have a large reserve of natural gas. Main exporting countries were Trinidad and Tobago, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia and Canada. Ammonia is sometimes transported by pipeline (most notably in the United States and Russia), but in most cases maritime transport is used.

The existing ammonia carrier fleet

Ammonia is mainly transported in a liquid form at -33°C in specialized gas tankers. These are commonly referred to as LPG carriers, short for 'liquified petroleum gas carriers', though they can carry other types of liquified gas too. Not all LPG carriers are able to transport ammonia. Smaller LPG carriers often have a pressurised tank, which is not suitable for ammonia transport (see Table 2.1).

Table 2.1 Properties of different types of LPG carrier ships. Source: [4]

	pressurized	fully refrigerated	semi refrigerated
Tanks			
Shape	Cylindrical	prismatic	Cylindrical / bi-lobe
Maximum pressure	18 bar	0,2 bar	5,9 bar
Typical sizes	Small coaster	Handy, medium or large gas carrier	Coaster or handy
Cargo handling			
Cooled	-	Yes	Yes
Pressurized	Yes	-	Yes
Cargo types and boiling temperatures			
Butane (-5 °C)	Yes ambient	Yes	Yes
Ammonia (-32 °C)	-	Yes	Yes
Propane (-46 °C)	Yes ambient	Yes	Yes
Ethane (-88 °C)	-	-	Yes
Ethylene (-103 °C)	-	-	Yes

Clarksons World Fleet Registry [5] was used to identify different characteristics of the worldwide LPG carrier fleet. According to this database, the current fleet consists of around 1,300 vessels. 758 of these vessels are potentially suitable for transporting ammonia. This means they can hold cargo at a temperature of -48 °C or below, and are not explicitly labelled with a negative 'ammonia cargo'

indication². 475 of those vessels have a positive ‘ammonia cargo’ indication, meaning they are definitely suitable for carrying ammonia.

The vessels that can transport ammonia are relatively small, with an average cargo capacity of 30,000 dead weight tonnes (DWT). The data shows an increase in the average size of the vessels over time (See Figure 2.1). Shipbuilding companies have recently received certification for ammonia carriers of 100,000 [6] and even 150,000 cubic metres [7] in size (roughly equivalent to 68,000 and 102,000 tonnes). This suggests the growth of average ammonia carrier capacity, as shown in Figure 2.1, has not reached its end.

Figure 2.1 Average cargo capacity (DWT) of new LPG carriers that are capable of carrying ammonia. Source: [5]

Given the current size of the market, it is likely only a small fraction of this fleet is currently used for transporting ammonia. TNO estimates that between 40 to 60 vessels are currently used to ship ammonia worldwide, because these have sufficient capacity annually to transport the earlier mentioned 10 million tonnes of NH₃. This means only 10% to 20% of the ships capable of carrying ammonia are actually used to do so. There are many ships in existence that could be repurposed to transport ammonia, if the demand and freight rates would rise quickly.

Compared to other types of vessels, the LPG carrier fleet is relatively young. Data shows a construction boom of ammonia-capable liquid gas carriers in 2015 (see figure 2.2). In 2014 construction of LPG carriers increased to nearly 180 ships. This was related to the shale oil (and LPG) boom in the US (see EIA 2024). Main ship building countries for LPG carriers are South Korea (60%), China (18%) and Japan (10%). Main yards are Hyundai, Daewoo and STX in South Korea and Jiangnan in China.

² The database specifies for LPG carriers whether they are capable of transporting ammonia or not. Unfortunately, this field is left blank for many vessels in the database. Analysis shows that these are almost exclusively vessels that can transport cargo at -48 °C.

Figure 2.2 Keels laid per year for LPG tankers suitable for ammonia shipping Source: [5]

The current amount of orders for new LPG carriers is considerable. In 2023 new orders for 5.3 million dead weight tonnes have been placed. According to BRS Group, shipowners already anticipate on the role of LPG and ammonia in the energy transition in the following decades [8].

Table 2.2 properties of different types of LPG carrier ships. Source: [8]

New Orders	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
LNG (cbm)	3,289,294	896,766	3,145,678	10,814,293	8,869,523	7,260,607	12,228,828	32,181,815	14,425,582
LPG (cbm)	3,790,371	26,768	1,252,298	1,935,041	2,531,197	2,513,693	5,968,054	2,715,882	8,020,022
Ferries & Ro-pax (Gt)	320,374	632,618	504,373	926,099	977,665	138,150	606,128	344,140	249,292
Cruise (Gt)	2,497,405	2,426,894	3,112,253	2,325,644	1,651,427	81,040	57,498	508,080	1,039,528
SST Chemical Carriers (Dwt)	2,232,324	931,557	477,744	389,535	429,749	626,410	896,570	983,021	990,617
Car carriers (cars)	203,192	19,248	38,310	20,830	34,715	21,150	265,611	685,850	726,980
Ro-Ro (lm)	47,001	55,142	46,138	124,727	30,426	8,263	41,060	37,744	6,800

New Orders (Dwt)	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
LNG	1,779,817	487,215	1,673,133	5,850,083	4,750,166	4,054,680	6,767,913	16,762,481	7,385,678
LPG	2,617,327	22,424	839,449	1,292,920	1,707,106	1,687,631	4,033,523	1,791,518	5,362,331
Ferries & Ro-Pax	72,004	150,953	119,354	232,815	210,678	49,316	199,433	75,917	37,587
Cruise	211,193	199,065	265,861	214,076	146,685	9,766	5,235	59,560	85,812
SST Chemical Carriers	2,232,324	931,557	477,744	389,535	429,749	626,410	896,570	983,021	990,617
Car carriers	560,122	43,337	106,428	51,171	102,447	55,791	696,169	1,788,126	1,665,092
Ro-Ro	153,076	167,217	154,144	333,412	139,185	31,301	331,559	139,282	56,500

3. Future demand for ammonia shipping

The long term development of the market for ammonia transport depends on two factors: the growth of the current markets for ammonia, and the development and growth of new markets.

Growth of the current ammonia shipping market

Expectation by the International Energy Agency (IEA) [2] is that demand for ammonia from current users, mainly fertilizer production, will grow from the current levels of 180 million tonnes to around 225 million tonnes in 2050, implying a growth of less than 1% per year. Increased efficiency in the use of fertilizers and in plastics production slows down demand growth for ammonia as a feedstock. Ammonia production for the current purposes is expected to remain primarily for local use. The demand for shipping is expected to grow accordingly, from 17 million tonnes to around 22 to 25 million tonnes in 2050.

Emerging demand for ammonia shipping from new markets

A new application of ammonia is its use as a so-called 'hydrogen carrier', i.e. a more convenient way to transport hydrogen over long distances. As the world moves away from large-scale use of fossil fuels and fossil-fuel derived hydrogen, demand for sustainably produced hydrogen is expected to grow. Main applications of sustainable hydrogen, according to a 2022 report by the Hydrogen Council, are expected to be:

- Use as a feedstock in industry
- Use as a fuel for transport applications (heavy duty vehicles, marine application and aviation)
- Use for building and industry heat
- Power generation

Production costs of renewable hydrogen mainly depends on localised costs of renewable energy production and electrolyser utilization [9]. Hydrogen production costs will vary significantly throughout the world. The Hydrogen Council expects costs to be the lowest in Middle East, South America, Southern Africa, US and China. Research by TNO [10] has shown that shipping costs will most likely be a very small part of the total cost of hydrogen. Therefore, it is expected hydrogen will be produced where it is cheapest to do so, and then exported to the locations where it is needed, like Europe, Japan and China (which has its own production, but could become a net importer due to growing demand) (see Figure 3.1).

Hydrogen can be transported via pipelines, but this requires a large investment in fixed infrastructure. Maritime transport is more flexible and more readily available, since only import/export terminals and ships are required. Ammonia is considered to be a good energy carrier for transport of hydrogen on ships, since the energy density of liquid ammonia is much higher than that of either pressurized or liquified hydrogen.

Figure 3.1 a scenario for the future of the international hydrogen trade. Source [9]

Ammonia can also be used as a maritime fuel. It does not contain carbon and therefore does not emit carbon dioxide, the most important greenhouse gas, when combusted. Currently ammonia-powered shipping is still in its infancy: Clarksons tracked only 4 orders for ammonia-powered vessels in 2023 [5].

Demand increase for ammonia from emergence of new markets

The size of the development of the market for trade of renewable ammonia will depend mainly on:

- The demand for ammonia as a hydrogen carrier, influenced by
 - demand for renewable hydrogen
 - differentiation in the price of hydrogen production between regions
- The demand for direct use of ammonia in shipping and in industry

Several studies present scenarios for the potential size of the new markets. All presented scenarios are considered to be their 'high growth' scenarios. Since the main question for this study is to find whether there will be capacity restrictions for the supply for shipping ammonia, this section will only consider these high growth scenarios.

- The Hydrogen Council and McKinsey report [9] foresees a total seaborne trade of ammonia of 500 million tonnes in 2050.
- In their high growth scenario, IRENA and the Ammonia Energy Association [11] predict that the total market for ammonia will grow to 680 MT in 2050. Use as a marine fuel accounts for roughly 200 MT³, use in industry and power generation account for 180 MT.
- In their Sustainable Development Scenario, IEA presents a similar growth of the total market up to 550 MT in 2050. Main new markets are again maritime (250 MT) and power supply (100 MT).

A growth scenario for the ammonia shipping market

In order to create a scenario for the potential growth of the market for ammonia shipping, the following assumptions were made:

- **The demand for shipping from current markets for ammonia is assumed to remain 10% of the production volume.** Production of fertilizer and other energy intensive industries are likely to be located close to areas with cheap energy.
- **The demand for trade for new markets is assumed to be significantly higher than 10% of production volume.**
 - Ship bunkering is concentrated in a few ports. The ports of Rotterdam and Antwerp are currently significant bunkering ports, that is linked to the petrochemical industry in these ports. The ports have well-developed bunkering infrastructure and associated services. It is however uncertain if the current position of these ports will remain so or if there will be a shift to locations that have easy access to renewable energy (such as the Middle East or North Africa). In a recent study, PBL, TNO and CE Delft estimated that up to 50% of the Dutch bunker market might shift to other locations. A reduction of 25% was assumed as a base scenario. It is assumed that 75% of the ammonia bunker volume for shipping is being transported via maritime to the bunker ports. For the other 25% it is assumed that the bunker volume will be sourced locally or that ammonia is transported via pipeline (e.g. in a port in the Middle East or Africa) [12].

³ This would be in line with 40% to 45% of the total maritime energy consumption. Since the first pilot vessels sailing on ammonia are currently only just in development, this would require a very significant part of all new builds from 2030 onwards to have an ammonia powertrain, as well as development of a retrofit market.

- All of the hydrogen for use in new industries and power supply is assumed to be shipped as ammonia. This volume is considered to be produced as a hydrogen carrier in order to facilitate transport to other areas.

Consequently, a significant increase of the shipped volume of ammonia is assumed under this high growth scenario. The potential volume increases by an order of magnitude, from 17 million tonnes per year to approximately 300 million tonnes per year (see Table 3.1 and Figure 3.2).

Table 3.1 - Future ammonia shipping demand scenario

	Production (Million Tonnes)	Share of maritime trade	Maritime trade volume (million tonnes)
Volume 2023	180	~10%	17
Development of existing market 2050	220	10%	22
Potential for Marine fuel	200	75%	150
Potential for power generation and new industry	150	100%	150
Potential total volume 2050	570		322

Figure 3.2 Demand scenario for ammonia shipping in 2050, per sector

In order to identify the required growth of the number of LPG carriers, we assume that the volume of the other products that are being carried in these tankers, such as LPG and ethylene, remains stable. We assume that newbuild vessels will have an average cargo capacity between 50,000 and 60,000 DWT. That is about twice that of the current average suitable LPG carrier, and in line with the steady increase in average vessel sizes visible in Figure 2.2. This would mean an increase in economies of scale compared to the current vessels. We also assume development of dedicated ammonia carriers which have a very high utilisation rate, with an average 14 loaded sailings per vessel per year.

Based on these assumptions, between 320 and 420 new ships would be needed over the period between 2030 and 2050, 16 to 21 additional newly built vessels per year on average.

4. Effects of increased demand on shipping availability

Ship building capacity will be able to meet increased demand

The increased amount of LPG carriers that would be required for the transport of ammonia is moderate, if the demand increase will be evenly spread over the years from 2030 to 2050. The fleet analysis shows that the ship building industry is able to accommodate a large peak in shipbuilding demand, since 180 LPG carriers were built in and shortly after 2015. Figure 4.1 shows that it is common to have large fluctuations in demand for different shipping segments. In 2021, for instance, there was a significant increase in the orders for container vessels due to increased demand in the COVID and post COVID period. In 2022 there was a large increase in the orders of LNG tankers due to worldwide high gas prices.

Orders (million Dwt)

Figure 4.1 – Orders per year in million DWT. Source: BRS [8]

Currently, around 1,300 vessels are being constructed each year [8]. The market sees at the moment an increase in the orderbook, but has a stable production capacity. This results in a longer average delivery time of new vessels. However, fluctuations in the orderbook are not uncommon in the last few decades (see Figure 4.2).

**World Orderbook (w.o) versus World Deliveries (w.d) in Number of ships
Ratio w.o/w.d = Average Delivery Time (ADT)**

Figure 4.2 - number of ships ordered (in total) and delivered (per year) Source: BRS [8]

As we have seen, shipyards can cope with rapid changes. However, the OECD warns of the likelihood of upcoming labour shortages in the shipbuilding sector. Over 40% of people working in the sector are expected to retire in the coming 10 years [13]. This means many new workers must be recruited, trained, and retained in coming years, even if automation would reduce the labour requirements in the sector. If the shipbuilding sector indeed faces labour shortages, this will impact prices and lead times for new build vessels.

Large-scale conversion of existing vessels to ammonia carriers is unlikely

Besides newbuilding vessels, retrofitting existing vessels could be another option for increasing ammonia shipping capacity. Several sources indicate that existing LPG or LNG vessels that currently are not suitable for transporting ammonia could be altered [14].

LPG carriers that are currently not capable of transporting ammonia are mostly smaller vessels with pressurised tanks (see chapter 2). Their average cargo capacity is 2,200 tonnes, compared to an average of 30,000 tonnes for (semi-)refrigerated vessels that are capable of transporting ammonia [5]. These vessels are used for short distance coastal transport. It seems unlikely that retrofitting a pressurised cargo vessels to a refrigerated tank will be cost-effective, since this required a complete change of storage tanks, equipment on board and way of working. Because of their small size, retrofitting those vessels would not lead to a large increase in global ammonia shipping capacity either.

Conversion of refrigerated gas carriers is technically more feasible. LNG carriers have cooling systems on board that can cool the cargo to -165 °C, low enough for transport of ammonia. However, in a study on the option for converting (land based) storage facilities for LNG to Ammonia, Fraunhofer concluded that the main restricting factor for transporting ammonia in LNG vessels is the material of the supply tank. Not all steels used in LNG tanks are suitable for storing ammonia. There is a risk of corrosion when transporting ammonia in ferrous nickel alloys and copper and zinc alloys. These materials are currently used in many LNG tanks. Furthermore, conversion would also require refitting of piping, valves, et cetera [17]. The study finds it is unlikely that current facilities would be adapted, but that it is possible to prepare new build facilities for accommodating both cargo types. From a cost perspective, this will most likely also be the case for LNG vessels.

Finally, the ammonia transport demand timeline does not necessitate the relatively costly short term solution of retrofitting existing vessels. Given the expectation of a gradual increase of demand for ammonia shipping, new builds and utilization of existing ammonia-ready vessels are more economical ways to meet this demand.

Compliance with emission regulations

A specific question asked by the HyDelta team on the availability of shipping was whether the vessels would be able to comply to EU and IMO environmental regulations. The table below presents targets set out by IMO and the European Commission. The targets set out by IMO and the EU for 2030 can be reached through improvements of operations and smaller technical innovations. The target for 2040 and further require use of sustainable energy carriers [12].

Table 4.1 greenhouse gas emission reduction targets for the maritime sectors as laid down in several agreements at the EU and global level (source: [18])

		2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
IMO Strategy	CO ₂ reduction target		20%		70%		100%
FuelEU Maritime	Reduction carbon intensity	2%	6%	14.5%	31%	62%	80%

RED			14.5%			
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Several options for use of sustainable fuels in maritime applications are currently being developed. These include sustainable diesel fuels (HVO, FAME, synthetic diesel), LNG, methanol, hydrogen and ammonia. This is supported by use of electricity (batteries for auxiliary engines use or onshore power supply). There is currently no clear path on the uptake of the different options. This will depend on technological development of engines (or fuel cells), experience with safe operations on board and the development and pricing of supply of different options (see [12] or [18] for an in-depth analysis of this topic).

The forecast scenarios in chapter 3 present a large growth of the production of green hydrogen and transport in the form of ammonia. In such a scenario, pricing of green ammonia as a marine fuel will likely be competitive compared to other options. Therefore, application of an ammonia power train would be a viable option for most new built vessels, including LPG / ammonia carriers. Ammonia engines and fuel cells are still in a relative early development stage and there is limited experience with safe operations of ammonia as fuel. Alternatives for new built vessels are methanol or LNG, which are both at a more advanced stage of development.

For existing LPG carriers, use of sustainable diesel fuels will be a likely option. Retrofitting these vessels to other energy carriers is expensive, because of the costs of replacing the power train, storage tanks and other elements such as the piping. As a first indication, the total costs for retrofitting a large scale 2-stroke vessel to use ammonia as a fuel are estimated to be between 10 to 13 million USD [17]. Furthermore, conversion often requires additional space onboard of the vessel due to the lower energy density of the alternative fuels and required safety distances (see [18] for an analysis of the consequences for six ship types). This makes conversion technically challenging, since space on board will have to be available in locations suitable for placement of new or expanded fuel tanks and, possibly, additional safety measures such as cofferdams or double walls. Due to these technical challenges, conversion is not an option for many existing vessels.

In short, the LPG carrier fleet can meet greenhouse gas emission reduction in multiple ways. It is likely most existing ships will reduce their emissions over the remainder of their lifetime by using bio- or synthetic diesel to attain compliance. New vessels can use one of the renewable fuel options. Which one is most suitable depends on many factors and must be decided by the ship owner on a case-by-case basis.

5. Potential barriers to growth of ammonia transportation

The potential growth of the demand for maritime transport of ammonia is very large. This will require a significant growth in of the LPG carrier fleet, since it is unlikely that it could be met by (retrofitting) the current fleet. The estimated required 400 additional vessels between 2030 and 2050 would mean 20 new vessels must be built every year. The construction boom of LPG carriers in 2015 and the current large order book show that this should not lead to problems.

Market dynamics

Shipbuilding is well known to be a highly cyclical market [19]. This is illustrated by changes in the time-charter and spot market rates during the 5-year period shown in Figure 5.1. Supply, demand and price of shipping and ship building change continuously. It is therefore likely that growth of the LPG carrier fleet (the supply) as well as growth of the trade of ammonia (the demand) will not follow a linear path. As shown in the past, surges in demand for transport often lead to a spike in freight rates. This in turn increases demand for shipbuilding capacity, leading to increases in lead times and temporary shortages of shipping capacity. It is therefore well possible that there will be periods with a scarcity of supply of LPG carriers, resulting in (very) high transport prices. The opposite situation can also occur – when supply of shipping capacity grows faster than demand, freight rates will temporarily plummet.

Figure 5.1 – Example of LPG time-charter and spot market rates over a 5-year period. Source: [20]

Shortage of crews and ship builders

Ammonia has been handled safely as a cargo for decades. Training courses are available as are qualified crews. However, if the demand for ammonia carriers grows, demand for trained crews will grow too. The shipping industry is already facing a shortage of trained staff, and finding and retaining people is seen as a challenge by many in the industry [21]. Many new or existing seafarers must be trained to work safely on ammonia carriers, especially if the ships would also use ammonia as a fuel. In that case, additional training and a new safety regime tailored to use of ammonia as a fuel are required [22].

Lack of qualified shipbuilders and crew could become a barrier to growth of the ammonia shipping market. Increasing recruitment and retention, increasing labour productivity, and (re)training of crews and shipbuilders are all important ways to address this problem.

Social acceptance

Lack of social acceptance of maritime transport of ammonia, or of its use as a fuel, could prevent growth of demand for ammonia. Ammonia is a corrosive, flammable, and highly toxic substance. Even short exposure to ammonia is highly damaging to the health of humans and animals. Crew, populated port areas, and nature are at great risk if accidents occur. Social acceptance was not covered in depth for this research project. It is recommended as a topic for further investigation.

6. Summary

In chapter 1, 4 research questions were posed. A summary of the answers to those questions is presented here.

What are the characteristics of the current fleet of vessels transporting ammonia?

The current fleet of ammonia carrying ships is relatively young. This is due to a spike in new builds of LPG carriers around 2014. There are 8 vessels in the Clarkson's ship database labelled suitable for ammonia transport, but only an estimated 10 % to 20 % of these ships is actually used for this purpose.

What are the expected developments in the fleet between 2025 and 2050?

The current market for ammonia shipping is expected to grow at a modest pace of under 1% per year on average. If demand for ammonia shipping grows, repurposing of existing ships or building of new LPG tankers could increase the available ammonia-carrying capacity quickly. These could also use ammonia as a low-emission marine fuel, similar to the way LNG carriers use LNG as cargo and fuel today. The average size of newly built ammonia carrying ships is expected to increase to between 50,000 DWT and 60,000 DWT, or even larger.

How do the developments in the fleet match with a high-growth scenario for the uptake of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier?

If ammonia will be widely used as a hydrogen carrier, demand for ammonia shipping could increase many times over in the coming decades. Recent history has shown the shipbuilding industry is able to quickly build large numbers of LPG carriers in response to rapid growth of demand. In addition, many existing ships are also able to carry ammonia, though they transport other types of cargo at this time.

Under which circumstances will lack of shipping capacity be a barrier to the uptake of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier?

Lack of shipping capacity will most likely not be a barrier to the uptake of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier. Current ships can be repurposed or new ships can be built quickly to meet any foreseeable increase in demand. However, since ship building is a highly cyclical market and supply of vessels follow periods of large trade growth, it is well possible that there will be periods with scarcity of supply, resulting in high transport prices.

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